

Title: computer vision

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INTRODUCTION:

Here's the abstract of my talk on computer vision: "Vision is one of the most important senses that humans have evolved into having. A large part of our brain is used in processing images and understanding the context behind it. It might come natural for humans to see an image and immediately recognize what the story is behind the images but it takes computers extensive calculations to perform simple tasks. Recently, with the advancement of silicon chips on Graphic Processing Units, Computer Vision has finally picked up its pace to be usable in real world products. Face-book's auto face tagging, Snapchat's mask filters are some of the examples of Computer Vision working in the real world today. Hence, my talk will emphasize what is needed for companies to get started with Computer Vision and how they can utilize this growing technology to their full advantage."